

Elasticity of Investment Financing Policy towards the Growth of Film Distribution Networks as an Effort to Redesign the Film Industry

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to analyze the influence of investment financing policies on the growth of film distribution networks. Investment financing policy is seen from the aspect of setting investment credit interest rates in banking. Meanwhile, the growth of the film distribution network can be seen from the aspect of the number of cinema screens in Indonesia. This research uses several variables, such as: Investment Credit Interest Rates at Bank Persero, Regional Development Banks, National Private Banks and Foreign and Joint Venture Banks. The time range used in this research is from 2014 - 2022. This research uses quantitative methods using multiple linear regression. The explanation of the analysis results uses Keynes and Schumpeter's theoretical approach. Based on the results of data analysis, it was concluded that the investment credit interest rate variable had a significant negative effect on the variable number of cinema screens, especially on the National Private Bank Investment Credit Interest Rate. The results of the coefficient of determination (adjusted R²) show that the influence of the number of cinema screens is 0.9492175. The higher the interest rate on investment credit, the lower the number of cinema screens.

KEYWORD: Cinema Screens, Credit Interest Rate, Mixed-Foreign Banks, National Private Banks, Regional Development Banks, State-owned Banks.

INTRODUCTION

There are several indicators in the development of the national film industry, namely (i) increasing the number of cinemas and screens; (ii) increasing the number of film productions; (iii) increasing the number of viewers of Indonesian films; and (iv) increasing the number of films entered at the Box Office (pultjakdibud, 2020). Apart from that, developments in communication technology need to be considered because they initiate digital platforms that encourage innovation in film distribution networks, such as the emergence of streaming services with video on demand. Based on statistical data, revenue from Indonesian video on demand subscriptions could reach USD 411 million in 2021 with user penetration of 16% in 2021 and is expected to increase to 20% in 2025.

The film industry as a mass media industry is a capital-intensive cultural industry so investment is needed to support the growth of the industry (Komalawati, 2017). In the national economy, films that pass censorship and are shown in cinemas are one component that can be included in PMTB (Gross Fixed Capital Formation) growth which has an impact on GDP (Gross Domestic Product). The government through the Ministry of BUMN formulated that the problem of national film lies in three main problems, namely financing, marketing and licensing (Thohir, 2023). Therefore, in efforts to redesign Indonesian film policy, these indicators and problems can be guided by, so that appropriate and competitive strategies can be obtained.

The importance of initiating aspects of film distribution has been carried out through the commemoration of National Film Day, March 30 2016, President Joko Widodo stated that at least Indonesia needed an additional 4,000 film screens, because at that time only 1,000 screens were available (Suhendra, 2016). This condition is considered very far away if you look at the population in Indonesia. For comparison, Beijing, with a population of around 15 million, has 5,000 screens. (Afriyadi, 2016) Global market research company Euromonitor International reports that developed countries have an average of 84.3 screens per million inhabitants. Meanwhile, Southeast Asia has an average of 30.2 screens per million population. Meanwhile, Indonesia only has 7.6 screens per million population with the total cinema screens from all operators in Indonesia until the end of 2022 estimated to be around 2,107 screens (Yuliana, 2023).

Distribution network development also needs to be balanced with investment policies. For this reason, the Coordinating Minister for the Economy, Darmin Nasution, on February 11 2016 issued a Policy Package Volume As a result, through Presidential Decree

Number 44 of 2016 which was signed by President Joko Widodo on 12 May 2016, the film business began to open to foreign investors starting from the production, distribution and exhibition sectors. Distribution and exhibition aspects are determining factors for the success of a film. Distribution is needed to expand the market and connect the production stage with consumption or connect filmmakers with their audiences (Smits, Higson, Mateer, Jones, & D'Ippolito, 2017). This means that film business actors and the government need to immediately take strategic steps and place the post-production stage as an important part of efforts to develop the national film industry.

A company from South Korea, CJ CGV Corporation, has become a major player by carrying out massive expansion into Indonesia after the Film Performance Industry was removed from the negative investment list. This is part of the company's expansion agenda into the Asian region. In the period 2015-2019. (R, Elake, & Manggarsari, 2022) In 2023, CGV will have 71 cinemas with a total of 408 screens. In its Annual report, CGV stated that it was still focused on opening new cinemas on the island of Java, which has the strongest economic growth compared to other regions in Indonesia (Saumi, 2023). Apart from CGV Blitz, several foreign investors have also joined the film industry.

PT Nusantara Sejahtera Raya, which is the leading cinema operator in Indonesia for the Cinema 21, Cinema XXI and The Premiere cinemas, signed a contract worth 3.5 trillion Rupiah with the Sovereign Wealth Fund from Singapore, the Government of Singapore Investment Corporation (GIC), in 2016 (R, Elake, & Manggarsari, 2022). The investment by GIC reflects the investment company's confidence in Indonesia's long-term growth potential. As of March 2023, Cinema XXI has presented 1,235 screens in 230 cinema locations spread across 71 cities throughout Indonesia, and will continue to grow to reach the target of 2,000 screens in the next 5 years. (Saumi, 2023)

In 2019, the Mexican company, Cinopolis, acquired 40% of the Lippo Group's Cinemaxx cinema chain for an estimated value of US\$110 or around IDR 1.5 trillion. Cinopolis currently operates 691 cinemas in 17 countries and has 5,609 screens. With a history of 50 years, the company is the second largest film network in the world in terms of viewership, reaching 338 million per year. In 2023, Cinopolis will have around 60 cinemas spread across various locations, with a total of around 289 screens. Generally, the locations of Cinopolis cinemas are in malls owned by the Lippo Group.

Apart from these three big players, the Agung Sedayu Group through Agung Sedayu Ritel Indonesia also operates the FLIX cinema. Currently, this Aguan affiliated company operates cinemas in 4 locations in Jakarta, with a total of 25 screens. Not to be left behind, the new issuer is PT Tripar Multivision Plus Tbk. (RAAM) which operates Platinum Cineplex in 11 locations, with a total of around 36 screens. RAAM operates its cinemas in cities which are tier 2 and tier 3 cities in Indonesia.

To strengthen the financing or investment aspect in developing the film industry, President Jokowi has changed the status of the State Film Production Public Company (PFN) to a corporation. The change in PFN's status is stated in Government Regulation (PP) No.42/2023 on 10 August 2023. This change has an impact on changing the PFN business process, which was originally focused on film production, but is now expanding, especially in the financing/investment aspect, to building a viable film ecosystem. known as a capital-intensive cultural industry.

Expansion and increasing the productivity of a company requires proportional capital. Capital is one of the production factors needed in long-term production theory. One alternative business funding that can be used is the use of investment credit by banks. Investment credit can meet a company's financial needs, apart from being able to help meet its financial needs, investment credit can increase development in various sectors and increase the number of goods and services (Kasmir, 2014). This type of credit usually lasts for a medium to long term, depending on the agreement that has been made by both parties.

Investment credit has an important role for individuals or business entities. Therefore, investment credit is able to help entrepreneurs in capitalizing their companies. In addition to companies, investment credit is very important for economic growth and development because banks must formulate strategies to support the distribution of banking credit to the community, especially in the business world. In research (Rosita, Ermani, & D, 2020), results were obtained that partially there was a significant influence of investment credit on economic growth, shown by an R-square score of 0.935. The progress of investment credit and economic growth during the 2006-2016 period experienced a fluctuating increase with an average of 28.34% for investment credit and 6.48% for economic growth respectively.

Based on Commercial Bank Reports (LBU), investment credit is long-term or medium-term credit distributed to prospective debtors to finance various capital goods for the creation of new projects, expansion, modernization or renovation, modernization. For example, procurement of various machines, land and buildings for factories where payments are based on business performance. Banks are institutions whose main activity is collecting funds from public sources and returning these funds to the community as well as providing other services (Kasmir, 2014). Banks act as intermediary institutions for issuing credit. Credit is a delay in repayment due from the percentage given now, whether in the form of money, goods or services (Wulandari, 2012)

Investment credit is generally used to expand a business or build new projects/facilities for redevelopment. For example, investment credit as financing for building a factory or purchasing machinery will later be used for a longer period of time (Abdullah & Suseno, 2004). Investment credit is provided by banks to purchase capital goods that will not expire in a business circulation, meaning that after several cycles the process is to withdraw cash and return it into cash after going through several cycles (Mulyono, 2001).

The amount of investment credit is influenced by the credit interest rate (base lending rate), where there are several calculation components including the cost of funds and other costs such as overhead costs, risk factors, spreads and taxes (Sawitri & Wicaksono, 2009). The Central Bank is an institution that has influence in determining interest rates as a reference in the money market. In Indonesia it is known as the Bank Indonesia Interest Rate (BI Rate). Changes in the BI interest rate (BI rate) are followed by changes in deposit interest rates and credit interest rates with movements in the same direction or positive (Ayu & Yunita, 2013). In investment credit distribution, the determination of the basic interest rate or minimum interest rate is stipulated in Bank Indonesia Circular Letter number 13/5DPNP dated 8 February 2011 concerning Transparency of Information on Basic Credit Interest Rates (SBDK).

Based on Bank Indonesia data, investment credit interest rates are grouped based on the type of provider bank into state-owned banks, government banks, national private banks, foreign and joint venture banks. In the period 2014 – 2022 there are fluctuations related to investment interest rates from these banking sources. The description is as follows:

This data shows that investment interest rates have decreased from 2014 to 2022. The lowest investment credit interest rates are given by foreign banks and joint venture banks, this can be seen in the yellow graph. Meanwhile, the highest investment credit interest rates are provided by Regional Government Banks which are shown in the orange graph.

Interest rates and investment have an inverse relationship, with the assumption that if interest rates rise then investment will decrease. Vice versa, if interest rates decrease then investment will increase. The lower the interest rate, the higher the investment demand will be. With lower interest rates, consumers, especially business people, will tend to make acquisitions or expansion.

This assumption is related to the development of cinema screen growth in the period 2014 - 2022 which also has a tendency to increase. Cinema screen growth data can be described as follows:

Head of BKPM Franky Sibarani in a press release in Jakarta, 20 July 2016 stated that the Investment Coordinating Board would encourage investment in the film sector, especially for the addition of cinemas or film screens before encouraging the progress of Indonesian films. Investment in additional cinema screens can increase the number of film productions. BKPM itself has received investment interest in the film sector from South Korea, Taiwan, the United Arab Emirates and the United States.

The increase in investment was attributed to the film's removal from the negative investment list. After the repeal, the number of cinema screens almost doubled from 900 screens in 2015 to 1,800 screens in 2018. Deputy Head of the Creative Economy Agency, Ricky Pesik, stated that the growth of cinema screens in the country is also considered to have implications for increasing the number of national film viewers from 16 million in 2015 to 50 million viewers in 2018, an increase of around three times.

This research aims to see the role of investment credit interest rate policies in Indonesia in the period 2014 – 2022 on the growth of cinema screens. Investment Credit Interest Rates are grouped based on the type of bank provider into State-owned Banks, Government Banks, National Private Banks, Foreign and Mixed Banks so that it is hoped that we can see a model of the influence of certain types of banking investment credit on the growth of cinema screens. So it is hoped that we can obtain appropriate recommendations to support the economic growth of the film sector in Indonesia.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Maynard Keynes' theory introduced a mixed economy, both the state and the private sector have an important role in economic activity. Keynesian theory or Keynesian theory was applied based on economic ideas in England in the 20th century. Keynes's theory states that there are macroeconomic trends that influence individual behavior in microeconomics. Keynes believed that economic problems were complex problems, not special or separate like the previous understanding, namely laissez faire economic theory. Keynes believed that knowledge of economics is not only related to money even though money is a driver of economic activity. It is hoped that government intervention in economic activities can manage consumer demand and supply through issued policies.

Keynes's theory is known and used in investment and economic activities. As previously discussed in Keynesianism, macroeconomic tendencies influence individual microeconomic behavior. In investment activities, Keynes's theory is that investment decisions are taken by comparing the Marginal Efficiency of Capital or MEC with the real interest rate.

Marginal Efficiency of Capital is the profit that will be obtained by investing capital. The higher the interest rate, the lower the investment. In Keynes's investment theory, in summary the expected profit is called MEC because:

1. If MEC's expected profit is greater than the interest rate then the investment can be made.
2. On the contrary, if the MEC is smaller than the interest rate, then investment cannot be made.
3. If the MEC is equal to the interest rate, the investment can be implemented or not.

The description above explains the nature of the relationship between investment size and interest rates. Therefore, Keynesian investment shows that the amount or size of an investment does not depend on returns or just one factor, but is influenced by the cost of capital or interest rates.

The MEC concept of investment shows the nature of the relationship between the amount of investment to be made and interest rates. There is an inverse relationship between interest rates and the level of investment in the economy.

These factors influence investors in making investment decisions that refer to Keynes' theory as Keynesian investment, including:

1. A sense of optimism arises when an individual or company is aware of future conditions and dares to invest and have an impact on the profits obtained later.
2. Supply and demand levels influence each other. Therefore, it will affect investment conditions because demand increases when the economic pace is increasing and has an impact on economic growth in the country.
3. Increasing public share capital causes marginal product to decrease. This reduces the value of MEC because marginal product is the additional output a firm obtains with one additional unit of capital.
4. Profitable and positive technological developments will influence investment even though interest rates remain fixed

Schumpeter's theory holds that capital accumulation is an important factor in determining a country's economic growth. However, Schumpeter also emphasized the role of entrepreneurs in carrying out every innovation to increase productivity. Schumpeter also thought that what was most important was the increase in output caused by economic development. Where in this case it emphasizes the importance of the role of entrepreneurs for every innovation produced in order to increase output. Thus, when a company obtains capital for investment development, it needs to be followed up with innovation through strategic management so that profits can be obtained that can be used as capital

The innovations by entrepreneurs in question can be in the form of:

1. Introducing new goods and new quality goods that consumers have not encountered before.
2. Introducing new production methods that are more effective and efficient.
3. Opening new markets for the company. This can be shown by the level of exports in order to expand the market for production.
4. Discovery of new economic sources.
5. Running a new organization in the industry.

When innovation occurs with the introduction of various new technologies, it will ultimately provide more profits which are an important source of funds for capital accumulation in companies that use these technologies. However, this advantage is more monopolistic because only a few companies use the new technology. Over time, the existence of this technology in the long term will lead to a process of imitation of this new technology from other entrepreneurs. So that it reduces monopolistic profits and in the end the innovation will spread itself according to the process.

RESEARCH METHODS

The data used in this research is secondary data in the form of time series data which includes data on investment credit interest rates from State Owned Banks, investment credit interest rates from Regional Government Banks, investment credit interest rates

from National Private Banks, investment credit interest rates from Foreign Banks and Mixture and data on the number of cinema screens. Data analysis was carried out through a combination of descriptive analysis and a quantitative approach through analysis of the influence of investment credit from various banks on the number of cinema screens. In addition, regression analysis is carried out, which is popularly known as pooled time series. This research aims to determine the strong correlation between the type of banking that provides investment credit services and the increase in the number of cinema screens in Indonesia in the period 2014 - 2022.

To measure the level of influence of the type of investment credit interest rate on the number of cinema screens, it is formulated using the following equation:

$G = \frac{X_t - (X_{t-1})}{(X_{t-1})} \times 100\%$. Where: G (Growth rate of variable X); t (specific Year Value); t-1 (Previous Year Value); X (Dependent or independent variable). Next, to see the effect of Investment Credit based on banking type on the number of cinema screens in Indonesia, using multiple linear regression analysis processed with Microsoft Excel with the basic model specifications as follows

$$LB = \beta_0 + \beta_1BP + \beta_2BPD + \beta_3BSB + \beta_3BAC + e$$

Where: LB “(Number of Cinema Screens); BP (Persero Bank Investment Credit Interest Rate); BPD (Regional Development Bank Investment Credit Interest Rate); BSB (National Private Bank Investment Credit Interest Rate); BAC (Foreign and Joint Stock Bank Investment Credit Interest Rate), β_0 (ith constant); $\beta_{1,2,3}$ (regression coefficient for each independent variable); e (standard error)

Statistical hypothesis testing in this research is measured from the t statistical value, the F statistical value and the coefficient of determination R2. The t test was carried out to see the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable individually by assuming that the other independent variables are constant. At the significance level $\alpha = 5\%$, the test used is as follows: H0 is rejected. H1 is accepted if the t statistic > t probability value (p value), which means the independent variable (X) has a significant effect on the dependent variable.

The F statistical test basically shows whether all the independent or independent variables included in the model have a joint influence on the dependent variable. The way to find out is by comparing the F-calculated value with the F-probability value (p value). If the calculated F value is greater than the F probability value (p value), then the alternative hypothesis is accepted, meaning that all independent variables jointly and significantly influence the dependent variable. Hypothesis used: H: $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = 0$, H1: there is at least one regression coefficient that is not equal to zero

Analysis to measure the model's ability to explain variations in independent variables. The coefficient of determination value is between 0 and 1 ($0 < R^2 < 1$), a small value (R2) means that the ability of the independent variables to explain variations in the independent variables is very limited. A value close to 1 means that the independent variable provides almost all the information needed to obtain predictions of variations in the dependent model. The higher the value of the coefficient of determination, the better the ability of the independent variable to explain the dependent variable

RESEARCH RESULT

Based on the results of statistical analysis of multiple linear regression calculations on the independent and dependent variables in this study, it can be described in the calculation results as follows:

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.96802834
R Square	0.93707887
Adjusted R Square	0.87415775
Standard Error	0.13627773
Observations	9

Multiple R (compound R) is a measure to measure the level (closeness) of the linear relationship between the dependent variable and all independent variables together. In the case of two variables (one dependent variable and one independent variable), the

quantity R (usually written in lower case for two variables) can be positive or negative (between -1 – 1), but for more than two variables, the quantity R is always a value positive (between 0 – 1). A larger R value (+ or -) indicates a stronger relationship. From these calculations, it shows that the Multiple R value is 0.96802834, which means it is positive, close to 1, so that the dependent variable and the independent variable have a high or strong relationship.

R Square (R²), often called the coefficient of determination, measures the goodness of fit of the regression equation; that is, it gives the proportion or percentage of total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variable. The R² value is between 0 – 1, and the model suitability is said to be better if R² is closer to 1. The measurement results show that R Square is 0.93707887 or close to 1. So the calculation model is correct.

Adjusted R Square. An important characteristic of R² is that its value is a never decreasing function of the number of independent variables in the model. Therefore, to compare the R² of two models, one must take into account the number of independent variables present in the model. This can be done using “adjusted R square”. The term adjustment means that the R² value has been adjusted to the number of variables (degrees of freedom) in the model. Indeed, this adjusted R² will also increase as the number of variables increases, but the increase is relatively small. Adjusted R Square is 0.87415775, close to 1.

Standard Error. It is the standard error of the estimate of the dependent variable (in our case demand). This figure is compared with the standard deviation of demand. The smaller the standard error number compared to the standard deviation number of demand, the more accurate the regression model is in making predictions. Standard Error 0.13627773.

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	4	1.10634204	0.27658551	14.8929129	0.01137899
Residual	4	0.07428648	0.01857162		
Total	8	1.18062852			

If we look at the ANOVA table, it shows that the value of the regression model formed is suitable for use because the Significance F or P-Value is close to 0. So by using a significance level of 5%, the existing sample provides the conclusion that the resulting model is adequate and can be used. Next, it is necessary to look at the parameter hypothesis test which aims to test whether the predictor variable has a significant effect on the response variable.

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.91655229	0.12033364	7.61675862	0.00159493
Bank Persero	0.4001026	0.825945421	0.48441772	0.65341885
Bank Pemerintah Daerah	0.89063557	0.518096653	1.71905293	0.1607281
Bank Swasta Nasional	-2.1458095	0.979552231	-2.1906024	0.09362909
Bank Asing dan Bank Campuran	0.02812301	0.364950519	0.07705978	0.94227656

From these data it shows that the variable with the P-Value closest to 0 is the National Private Bank, while other variables have a P-Value that is more than 0. So H₀ is accepted in other words, for the variables State-owned Bank, Regional Government Bank and Foreign Bank and Bank Mixan there is no significant influence between the intercept value and the variable number of cinema s. So it needs to be taken out and re-formulated and calculated with a focus on taking the National Private Bank variable directly linked to the number of cinema s. The results of the recalculation are as follows:

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.9356153
R Square	0.87537599
Adjusted R Square	0.85757256
Standard Error	0.14498013
Observations	9

ANOVA	After		Before	
	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	49.1689508	0.000209302	14.8929129	0.01137899
Residual				
Total				

Based on recalculations, it shows that Multiple R, R Square, and Adjusted R Square are close to 1. Apart from that, the standard error is also close to 0 so the model is correct. Then, if you look at the ANOVA table, the significant F value after separating variables that do not have a significant effect shows a value that is much smaller and smaller than alpha.

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	1.05762003	0.08000738	13.2190309	3.3135E-06
Bank Swasta Nasional - Investasi	-0.9492175	0.135369326	-7.0120575	0.0002093

Based on the table, it shows that the P-Value is 0.0002093 (close to 0) so that using a significance level of 5%, the existing sample concludes that there is a significant influence between National Private Bank Investment Credit Interest Rates on the number of cinema screens in Indonesia. So the correct regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = 1.05762003 - 0.9492175X_i$$

Where every additional 1 unit in the credit interest rate will reduce the number of screen in the cinema by 0.9492175. This means that there is an inverse relationship between Investment Credit Interest Rates at National Private Banks. Likewise, if there is a 1 unit decrease in the National Private Bank credit interest rate, it will reduce the number of screen in cinemas by 0.9492175.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of multiple linear regression calculations on the influence of investment credit interest rates at Bank Persero, Regional Development Banks, National Private Banks, Foreign and Mixed Banks, the correlation with the strongest significant influence is on the National Private Bank variable. Thus, the role of national private banks is more dominant in supporting the growth of cinema screens in Indonesia in the period 2014 - 2022. According to the OJK, National Private Banks are banks with most or all of their shares owned by the national private sector. Some examples of national private banks are BCA, CIMB Niaga, Permata Indonesia, Bank Muamalat, Bank Danamon and etc.

The cinema industry's interest in investment interest rates from National Private Banks is demonstrated by corporate policies regarding investment plans to be carried out. The issuer that manages the CGV cinema network, PT Graha Layar Prima Tbk. (BLTZ) signed a credit facility agreement with PT Bank KB Bukopin Tbk. (BBKP) worth IDR 160 billion. Graha Layar Prima Director Park Seong Ho in his official statement on December 4 2023, said that the term loan facility from BBKP has a tenor of 1 year until December 2024. The collateral document for obtaining this loan facility is a corporate guarantee from CJ CGV Co. Ltd, as the

controlling shareholder of BLTZ. The purpose of this loan facility is a take over loan from The Export Import Bank of Korea [KEXIM].

The role of government banking institutions has not had a significant impact on the growth rate of cinema screens in Indonesia. If we look at the table of investment credit interest rates, it can be seen that Regional Development Bank interest rates tend to be higher. So by using a Keynesian theoretical approach, it does not arouse the interest of business people in the film distribution sector, especially cinemas, to synergize with the two banks.

However, there is an anomaly, where the investment credit interest rates for State-owned Banks and Joint Foreign Banks are actually lower than the National Private Interest Rates. However, these two banks did not actually have a significant influence. These data findings require further research to obtain a more detailed picture. The possibility that can be predicted using the Keynesian Theory approach related to Marginal Efficiency of Capital shows that there are no facilities that are closely related to the film business ecosystem from the two banks or there are mechanisms that create a barrier to entry so that even though the credit interest rate is low, it does not have a significant impact on number of cinema screens in Indonesia.

Another assumption can be used with a Schumpeterian theoretical approach where the innovation aspect of business actors or companies becomes an important aspect in creating economic growth. This means that even though the investment credit interest rate obtained is small, there is no growth due to the low level of innovation from industry players. So the resulting effects do not contribute to increasing economic growth. Therefore, innovative policies are needed in managing investment credit capital used by a company.

The sensitivity of investment interest rates to the development of film distribution networks can be input for the government in resolving film industry problems presented by the Ministry of BUMN. It can also be used as input for the transformation of PFN's business into an institution that handles financing/investment in building a national film ecosystem.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this research, the following conclusions were obtained:

1. Investment credit interest rates have a negative influence on the growth of cinemas in Indonesia, especially for the period 2014 - 2022. The influence is significant, especially on investment credit interest rates at National Private Banks. Where the higher the Investment Credit Interest Rate, the number of cinemas will decrease, while if the interest rate falls, the number of cinemas has the potential to increase.
2. Regional Development Bank Investment Credit Interest Rates are higher compared to National Private Banks, so the Keynesian Investment Theory approach is not in accordance with the concept of Marginal Efficiency of Capital. So the Regional Development Bank Investment Credit Interest Rate does not have a significant influence on the growth of cinemas in Indonesia in the period 2014 – 2022
3. There is an anomaly in the Investment Credit Interest Rates of State-Owned Banks and Joint Foreign Banks, even though they have lower Investment Credit Interest Rates compared to National Private Banks, the regression calculation shows that the relationship has no effect. So further research needs to be done to explain this phenomenon.

SUGGESTION

Based on the results of this research, there are several suggestions as follows:

1. With a Keynesian investment theory approach, to support the program to increase the number of cinemas, it is necessary to have a national policy that keeps investment credit interest rates from decreasing. A significant increase could affect the number of cinemas growing in Indonesia.
2. To bridge the problem of cinema growth in regions which is still minimal, it is necessary to regulate the investment credit interest rates of Regional Development Banks. Through Keynesian investment theory, low interest rates can have the effect of increasing cinema investment in the region.
3. To improve the results of this research, with the emergence of anomalies in the influence of investment credit interest rates for State-owned Banks and Joint-Foreign Banks, it is necessary to carry out further research to determine what other variables need to be added or other research methods.

4. With a Schumpeterian theoretical approach, investment credit interest rate policies need to be balanced with strategic management regarding a company's investment. So that capital from investment credit can increase profits which has an impact on adding new capital and also encouraging economic growth.

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